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Transcript

Hello, my name is...My name is Anna Makarudze and I'm doing a master's in software engineering technology. And I'm conducting research on investigating how developers in Mendez perceive vulnerabilities in open source development, including their project, especially given the rise of supply chain attack. And my study is focused on five web premise, Django, Next.js, Springboot, Laraville, and Ruby on Rails. Just a few things about ethical considerations.

Participation in SEC is entirely voluntary, and you can withdraw from the interview anytime. Will not retain any personal data or identifiable information, and will not share your name or e-mail address. or NI identifiable details and will not publish them.

You can also skip some questions that you're not comfortable answering. Your responses will be more anonymous and will not be linked to you for the projects you represent. And the interviews will be recorded and kept for the duration of the study to allow supervisors to identify the authenticity of the project data after which they'll be deleted.

So that's all.

And before you start, maybe could you please introduce yourself and the project that you're a developer or contributor to, and also the web framework that you use mostly, and how long you've been working with the web framework, how many years of experience you have as a software developer, all that.

Speaker 2

Can you take back your question? It seems the connection is a bit late on your side.

Speaker 1

Ah, okay.

Speaker 1

Could you please introduce yourself? Maybe tell us the web framework that you use mostly and also your level of experience with the web framework as well as your experience in the software development industry.

Speaker 2

OK. I'm a software engineer with over 8 years of experience. On front end, I've mainly been working with Laravel and Angular. Those are the two main frameworks that I've been using, I think, for almost six years. And I've worked on a number of enterprise projects using those frameworks. Yeah, I don't know if I missed anything that you might be interested in knowing.

Speaker 1

Okay. Do you maintain any open source projects or the projects that we could mostly enterprises commercial?

Speaker 2

Because of my Because of my commitment to my workers, I think for the past six years, I've been working for two companies simultaneously. And because both companies are like tech companies that handle a lot of projects from various companies of various sizes, I haven't had an opportunity to really involve myself too much in maintaining any open source, at least not hands-on, but just maybe oral participation and maybe just contribution and just reviews here and there. Yes.

Speaker 1

Thank you. okay um my research is mostly funded centered on security so I want to know how are security issues uh handled in the projects that you work on?

Speaker 2

Okay um you'll find that uh because of the commitment that we have of trying to always deliver on our work uh And I think this goes for many companies, maybe to depend on their sizes. But from speaking from my experience with the companies that I've worked with, you'll find that in most instances, we are just doing what we call, what's the term, whereby you're just trusting that the owners of this or the maintainers or creators of this package

There are-- because there's this tendency whereby the creators, let's say, for example, Laravel, the creators of it, they want to make sure that developers and even their maybe benefactors, they trust them enough to make sure that they deliver something that is secure, that can be used at an enterprise level.

So usually, what happens is you-- We have to depend on maybe, for example, GitHub, you can look at the reviews by other developers or companies.

And also, sometimes we have to pay attention to, if you have seen events like LaraCon, where you have to hear what they are talking about and what improvements they have done whenever there's an update or if there's a vulnerability that they addressed.

So we keep track of those so that whenever we are working with whatever new feature that they introduce, we are not blindly falling for it. At least we have like a high level understanding of what we're working with.

But to say that we really go through the codes, you know, it becomes another task on its own to say, okay, we are going through the library of Laravel and want to see all their dependencies, how their code is structured.

Usually their factories are just huge, they're lengthy, it becomes a job on its own. So what we do usually is we try and avoid to, like, if we have an existing project that is working well, we do not expose it to any newly introduced features that have been introduced in, let's say, Laravel, right?

Because sometimes they tend to be breaking changes that will not disturb the whole system. So there's what you call maybe compartmentalization, whereby if we feel like, OK, this feature is going to benefit us in some way, we try to work on it in a--in a controlled environment without exposing the existing working projects, because that's the only way you can guarantee safety as of now. Yeah.

Speaker 1

All right. And when you are working with Laravel, on Laravel projects, do you add dependencies that are outside of Laravel, or do you only use Laravel if it is out-of-the-box?

Speaker 2

Yeah, that's an important question because you'll find that, at least from our company, when we're just, at least when we're juniors, there was a time when sometimes we just trust a package because it has a lot of downloads, or maybe because if you go and check it on maybe NPM, you'll find that maybe it has some active maintainers based on maybe recent dates and updates that they may be showing there.

But you'll find that because of how, especially, I can talk of maybe the past two, three years with the introduction of AI, you'll find that some of these developers, at least the small communities and their packages that I entered, maybe one guy was just doing a hobby

project, we tend to avoid them now because you notice that some of these packages, they actually also depend on other packages.

And I don't know if you follow tech trends that much, like the recent vulnerability that attacked Axios. It was something that, that is a three hour window, but actually affected others. So because of that, to answer your question, we've avoided being too excited about using third-party packages.

Mainly, we focus on the ones that are provided by the main company or entity that is maintaining or creating the framework, in this case, Laravel. That's the way we can minimize unnecessary, you know, damage control. And also you'll find that with experience, we've also adopted a culture whereby there are certain features that we realize that, okay, if one guy can create this package and we know that we need it maybe for a long term, sometimes we end up creating some of those packages on our own. At least we have reached that level as a company. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Thank you. Okay. I think maybe you might have addressed it in a bit, but I'll ask, how aware are you of the dangers that vulnerable dependents present to your project, supposing you are using them?

Speaker 2

Okay. I hope I'll answer that question correctly. You'll find that. Because we're in active development, and like I said, that we develop systems and to maintain them for other companies, for us to keep at least a decent relationship with our clients and also to ensure that our reputation will expand beyond the clients that we have currently, we are forced to keep track of almost every package that we use.

And also, we take things like and the like. And also, our own production system, because of now CI/CD pipelines, we make sure that any vulnerabilities that are flagged before production, that piece of code, no matter how urgent it is needed, we make sure that it never goes to production because it tends to ruin, what do you call it, our clients.

And also this thing about, what do you call it, the supply chain vulnerabilities, whereby you find that you trust a package, but that package also is depending on other packages. So now it brings back the point that I said earlier, whereby we say we are not going to use a package that you don't trust enough, or at least

For smaller packages that we know, OK, we need-- let's say I'll give a simple example of-- this is just a small example. To say, maybe we want a feature whereby we want to print or to export data from someone's database using in a maybe Excel format or PDF format.

A simple thing like that, you assume, OK, what harm could it bring if I just install some guy's package that can access the data? But then you find that that's how most people are being attacked.

Because now, you know, our hackers will always look for the weakest points. So coming back to the point about supply chain vulnerabilities, if people realize that, okay, this package is being used, maybe it's having maybe an average of 10,000 downloads in a week.

They will just go and scout for any vulnerabilities. Maybe they'll manipulate a package that is being used by that package that you're using. So now, because they can't really attack the main system, they'll attack a package of a package.

So we try by all means to avoid, especially those packages that have, what do you call it, either a small group that doesn't have at least social proof. Maybe just see it as a lot of downloads because some guys are maybe good at marketing themselves, maybe on Reddit.

And some junior developers or some script kids, they'll just go and download it for, just for, out of excitement, maybe for all for experiments. So if you depend your or if you put all your trust in the number of downloads sometimes, though it's a valid point to use, that's why some people are missing the map, because now you're trusting that, okay, because it is a lot of downloads, maybe it's good, but maybe it was downloaded by a bunch of kids who were told that this

This package is good. So as a company, speaking from my experience, we've avoided a situation whereby we just download the package just because it's popular. And like I said, even if we were to get access to some of our codes, you'll notice that we are that one company that avoids using packages as much as they can.

We focus on the main framework. If there's anything that we need to build it to our source, because if there's any vulnerability, we know where to look.

Speaker 1

Thank you. You mentioned that you use your CI/CD pipeline to check for vulnerabilities. Could you kindly maybe share more on that, what tools you use in that process?

Speaker 2

Okay, so what happens is we have our own testers internally. So usually as the development team, we just do the development, we push the code, and there's a testing team that handles that, because mainly we have a DevOps team that handles that. But on our side as the developers, usually, We just rely on things like, what do you call it? I think it's Renovate. Renovate and is it Dependabot? Yeah, I think it is Dependabot. And there's this recent one that came recently, whereby we use them to scan all the packages that we're using.

And if no issues are flagged, then we can trust them enough to use them. But also there's another testing team that will handle that. Yeah.

Speaker 1

And apart from the testing team, do you have sort of like a security team within your organization or slipped to the testing team?

Speaker 2

Come again, you're glitching there.

Speaker 1

All right. I was asking, apart from the testers, do you have like sort of a security team that is responsible for security within the organization?

Speaker 2

Okay, not necessarily, because usually we do, when you create the softwares that we use, we do a handover, takeover. So we just maintain relationships with companies whereby if they need any assistance from us as they develop, as they come and that develops or maintains their systems, that's what will come in.

Otherwise, they have their security terms because sometimes we work with banks and sometimes we work with big companies. I don't know if I'm supposed to do this. If I'm not, just delete it. But we also work with companies like

It's a big company, but you'll find that they have branches, at least like in the nation that I'm in. So we've had opportunities whereby we create certain softwares, and they take them-- they test them to integrate them with the already existing ecosystem that they have. So I find that sometimes our-- our levels of access become limited once they integrate the systems with their own into their own ecosystem.

So we have never really invested in a security team, at least from as far as I know, because our company is not that big. So at least you almost know every developer is within the company. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Thank you. All right. What influences the decision to update to newer versions of either the dependencies or the web framework that you're using, since you said you mostly rely on the lot of the workflow itself?

Speaker 2

OK, so you find that we are not the kind of people, like I said earlier, that we are not the kind of people who get excited about new features, right? Because you'll find that not every new feature that is introduced in a framework is really addressing your issue at hand. So usually, if ever we feel like there's a new feature that we might use, maybe in Laravel or Spring Boot or Angular, what we do is we wait until such a time as maybe we have a new project that we are working on.

That's when we say, OK, let's make use of the new version of Laravel or the new version of Angular. Because you find that, like I said, we are building systems for other companies. So you can't then just rush to a company and say, you know what?

Angular is because most of these clients, they don't even know about these things. I mean, the text that we use, they just tell you, I want this system, blah, blah, blah, you know. Yes, of course, they have their IT team, maybe they are developers internally that might know one or two things for maintenance that might not require us to get involved.

So we find that we never really rush to upgrade systems that are already in production. Unless if there's a security vulnerability that has been introduced to say, you know what, maybe version 21.1 has this issue. So we introduce version 21.1.1 to address that, that is a security patch.

Then we know, okay, our systems are exposed, we need to make this upgrade. Other than that, we don't introduce, we don't just jump into a new version for the sake of joining the bandwagon.

We don't do that. It exposes us to more risks because also you have to put into consideration that after the internal tests come and let's say a lot of you, after introducing certain features in a certain version, it becomes a target also, because remember, there's always a crew that is waiting to exploit the vulnerabilities within the new version.

So if you just jump in to say, okay, there's a new version, let's jump in you become part of the victims if ever there is what a vulnerability within that upgrade so usually we do not do upgrades to any existing software like the ruin programming says if it works don't touch it we follow it strictly yeah and.

Speaker 1

On the off chance that you use dependencies, how do you check whether they are still being maintained?

Speaker 2

The one usually you just have to rely on either if the repos are accessible, you can check the repos whenever there are updates. Usually those guys though write it in their notes or if they have a repository elsewhere outside of GitHub or let's say like the. Most note packages, you can just find them on NPM.

So usually you go there and you also see the dates, you track the dates of when it was last updated and what prompted the update. Because sometimes the update really is not, like I said, it's not addressing something that you have at hand.

So usually that's the best way you can track. And also, like I said, We avoid just, what do you call it, pulling every package that you see on the web. We try to strictly use packages that are within the ecosystem of the main framework.

That way, we know that at least there's an active maintenance going on, even if they don't announce it every now and then.

Speaker 1

Suppose you mentioned using GitHub Dependabot. Suppose it flags some dependence that's being vulnerable. How do you handle that?

Speaker 2

Okay, if it's a dependency that has been flagged, that means we're not supposed to use it. Because at the end of the day, you can't go back to a client and say, you know what, reflect this on GitHub. Maybe you're talking to just an accountant who just said, Guys, I want a software that handles my...He doesn't know about GitHub, he doesn't know about dependencies.

So this is an internal decision that you make to say, Guys, do we really stop working on this project because this package has been flagged? What's the workaround? So that's when we, that point I said also earlier on to say, there are certain features that we have told

ourselves we have to build them ourselves, 'cause I'll tell you. The world has been intrigued so far into believing that you have to solely depend on the big tech for solutions or maybe on a certain group of people.

But now, just if you allow me to just sway a bit, you'll find that with the new policies like currently that are being introduced in different parts of the world, whether they are talking about, if this is political, please feel free to remove it, but it affects everyone, almost everyone.

They are saying we want to introduce ID verification, edge verification, and the like. Now you find that most people, because they have been using maybe Microsoft for a long time, or Windows, to say, for a long time now, they're like, OK, because they decided this, we have no choice.

We just have to comply. No, that's what the world has been made to believe. But when you are someone who is a developer, as you gain experience and as you see how the world is being shifted, you'll find that some of these policies, they're being introduced by people with a certain agenda that might not

That is not sometimes supposed to be enforced on everyone. So I'm giving this example why. You'll find that, like, I'm a Linux user, and you realize that one of the pioneers or maintainers of Ash Linux is saying, we want to comply with the policy that has been introduced maybe in Texas. And I'm in Africa.

I have no need to give a Texas governor my ID. I don't wish to be in Texas. So here's the thing. What do I make a full of existing kennel?

Sorry, I need to hang up this call.

You'll find that I'll just make a system and I work my way to stay in the game, but without complying with rules that don't apply to me. You understand? So I'm saying this to address your question where you said, what happens when a package is flagged by Dependabot? The thing is, as a developer, I know we're at different levels. You have to get to a point whereby you have to avoid being too dependent on other developers' ideas or limitations, because at the end of the day, you're just a script kid if you're like that. Be willing to get your hands dirty. Try and make your own packages. It might not be perfect, but almost every package that is out there started as an experiment by someone, because they've experienced a certain limitation or a certain issue with the existing technology. I think, as the statement says, the best solution providers are those who encounter the problem firsthand. I think it's a motto that we live by as developers, at least within my team. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Thank you for that. Okay.

Speaker 2

Okay.

Speaker 1

Alright, so. I don't know if this question applies since you avoid using and dependencies wherever possible, but in the off chance that you do use them, how long does it take for you to have to update a vulnerable dependence within your project? Supposing you have them or is it something that you quickly do?

Speaker 2

OK, depending on the on the extents of the of the vulnerability, or maybe if it's a malware that has been introduced within the dependence, it now comes back to how much we are depending on that package and how severe it is. Because, I mean, there are certain pages that you just flag, and within an hour, you resolve them. So I'll be lying if I say there's a specific timeline to how much time we take to resolve an issue. I'm sure you've had experiences with big tech at least in the past one year or two years or so. You have seen what has happened with Facebook, you have seen what has happened with which other big tech recently got a third uh is is sleeping my sleeping my mind uh but I'm sure you know some of those companies all I'm saying is you have seen all these companies they have this policy where they say uh our systems are always 98 to 99% they've been 98 to 99% uptime policy but I'm sure you saw what happened with yeah Amazon web services they solve their issue within the time of their stipulated policies right so it shouldn't be it will be misleading if I say we have like a time a stipulated stamper it always depends on the severity of the vulnerability.

Speaker 1

Okay so uh you mentioned that sometimes you develop things yourself because you don't want to rely on dependencies. But I've noticed in some ecosystems, if there's a package that is safely used and that's not longer being maintained, some community members might step up to take over that dependency and maintain them. Is this something that happens within the PHP and that are for community where you step up and handle a dependency, or maybe you take it and modify and maintain it yourself. I don't know.

Speaker 2

I missed some of your words, but you're asking if we have ever, because there was a glitch in the network, but you're asking if we have ever in an existing library.

Speaker 1

Yes, and taken it over because it's one of... Okay.

Speaker 2

No, no, we've never. The only time we did that, the only time we did that, we actually took just one package. It was to do with, it was actually to do with, it was just a package for exporting, what do you call them, Excel files. So you realize that there's a package that was really used by a number of guys, but we noticed that it would not produce or it could not like export multi-page Excel files or PDFs, right? So we actually took it and we had to like patch it up so that it met our needs. That was the only time. Other than that, no, we have never.

Because we always say it's easier to create something from the ground up than to start someone else's code and then try to, though it's effective, but you'll find that almost everyone who does that, either it's a company that has enough resources to hire a lot of people and some will be saying, it will be designated to maintaining or to patch up a certain package while these others are working on the main projects. So for our company, we avoid such burdens because it's not that big. It's not that big. So almost everyone is always working on a project that is facing a very close deadline. So we never really adopt any packages to maintain them.

Speaker 1

And then have any of your projects ever been exposed to supply chain attacks?

Speaker 2

Yeah, actually, there was one.

Speaker 1

OK.

Speaker 2

It was actually embarrassing. But yeah. OK. Yeah. Yeah, there was one. And it's actually a payment gateway. And so it was it was now like inflating people's like balances, you know, like I don't know what happens because I like like already, you know, I mostly work on the front end.

So it was something that's mainly affected the Spring Boot API, but I also do Spring Boot within my company. So it was actually now messing up with people's balances. So we now ended up having legal issues with the bank that was incubating the payment gateway. But

it was something that was quickly addressed, but you know, you end up answering questions like, no, you guys Maybe you're trying to manipulate the system so that you make profits, but it was never the case. Thank God that when, like I said, when we create some of these systems, we end up integrating with ecosystems of other big companies. So fortunately, some of the work was being also handled by the internal team of the bank, you know. So no, they understood what was happening and that it wasn't on our side.

So it brings back the point where I said, we avoid, by all means, where we can, we avoid using third-party packages, especially these small ones that just maybe someone saw the project that tends to be adopted by the community. Because those guys, they have dissonance of just waking up and saying, you know what guys are? I'm not too busy to maintain this, so they're leaving. Or they are assigned it to some guy who is reckless. And that guy maybe exposes a certain key that then grants license to another guy who's going to mess the whole thing up because he's trying to target another government or whatever for just making them for themselves. So yeah, we have had that experience.

Speaker 1

Okay. Was that to a dependency or something else? If you don't mind sharing.

Speaker 2

No, it was, it was, it was, it was actually a dependency. It was actually a dependency because if you find, you'll find out that there's a lot of Java, I mean JavaScript libraries out there, some that will work for you, they'll be addressing the issue at hand, but then because The developer was focusing on just addressing that issue. Maybe they just leave the code exposed. And then another guy just catches something that is malicious. So it was actually a third-party package that we're using. Because primarily, like I said, we don't entertain third-party packages. We use them. It would be terrible if I say we don't use them because, I mean, most of these frameworks, they come with certain packages whereby if you don't adopt them, it won't work for you. So yes, we use them. But where we can avoid, we try to avoid because, yeah, it's terrible.

Speaker 1

Yes, you mentioned using Angular in your projects, meaning to say you rely also on javascript library.

Speaker 2

Yeah, mostly I would say typescript, but of course it's a superset of javascript. Yeah.

Speaker 1

All right. So my other question was what other practices do you have for mitigation of supply chain attacks other than avoiding dependencies when you can?

Speaker 2

Um I don't think we have much outside that. I don't think we have much outside that because it's always about, or already I think that I've mentioned, keeping track of the progress that maintainers or the developers of that certain packages, what they're doing, any issues that they're addressing, then we see what we need to use and we use it. But by all means, I come back to the self-statements.

We avoid them. Yeah, we avoid.

Speaker 1

OK. Do you face any challenges addressing vulnerable dependencies within your projects? Or since you avoid them, maybe you don't face as many challenges.

Speaker 2

I think the only time I had that experience was, I think, around 2020, 2021, when I actually needed a feature. I think that question is one of the top engaged questions. I don't know, since I haven't been on that Laravel-- it's like the-- It's like the, what do you call it? The Stackoverflow of Laravel, right? I don't know if you've ever been there. I remember there was a feature that I wanted, because by then I was just a script, at least in Laravel.

What was the feature for? You know, the funny thing is it was something that was actually in active development. And it was only later introduced about three months later after, it is from the day that I posed that question within the community.

So guys, I need this feature. And someone was like, it actually has to do with filament. I don't know if you do development. Yeah. So it's actually to do with filament. And I remember the guys actually saying, you know what, just realize something is cooking, right? I was like, OK, maybe this is just one of those guys who's talking. But you'll find that The guys from most of these main packages that are maintained by Laravel, they are actually active in those communities. So they actually picked some of the ideas from there.

So that was the only time that I actually had an issue with the third party package that I had to actually wait for like three months. No one had told me to wait, but I'd actually given up on that idea because I was like, well, this is beyond my abilities. But at least about three months from that time, I remember vividly because it was something that I really wanted.

That was the only time. Other than that, I've never had an issue with the package that I put on GSO, none.

Speaker 1

All right. And do you have any recommendations for other developers on how they can avoid supply chain attacks due to dependencies?

Speaker 2

I think the first one, like I said, if your system works, don't get any big ideas of just changing it for the sake of changing. I know as developers, there's this temptation whereby after reaching a certain level with a project, you have this feeling in you that tells you, no, you can take it further, right?

So my advice is, if your project works, right, I know some of these things are not new, but if your project works, if your system works, at least let that one run independently. And if you feel like you need to make any updates, do them separately. And also, don't be, if you're a developer, avoid being a script kid.

Sometimes Take time, whenever I get the slightest time, take time to see how other people are coming up with the ideas that you end up just forking and using. At least fork them and try to understand them and see if you can build it for yourself.

I know for someone who is new to software development, I was once there, you'd be like, eh, no, I can't do this. But you find out that most of the ideas that are being adopted in the world

It was just someone who was doing an experiment, maybe a hobby, maybe it was just a simple challenge, but it becomes something that the world adopts. So the best is learn to study how others are doing it. And try to play around with it, see if you can come up with something. Trust me, you'll go far.

And I think finally, what I can say is AI is here to stay. And people should avoid using it as a clutch, because that's one thing that is ruining software engineering currently, especially with these packages, because sometimes you focus someone's idea that was actually good, then you try to think you can outsmart that person by writing a prompt into cloud code and then think you can maybe improve that code using AI.

I mean, AI is just working on something that is already being worked on by people already. It won't introduce anything new, at least not for now. So my advice is people should avoid using AI as a clutch. It's dangerous. Yeah.

Speaker 1

Can you explain the concept you keep mentioning of ScriptKid? It's the first time that I've heard it.

Speaker 2

Yes, FaceTime. Okay. I hope you write it down. Then you just look it up or just punch it into your chatbot. Ask what is a script kid. So a script kid is someone who is, how can I put it? It's someone who just uses what has already been created by others without even understanding how it works. That's a script kid.

So it's like right now, if you were to say, hey, man, I need you to help me build this, this, this. I will build it and give it to you. Then you ask me, can you explain what you did? I go no. That's a script kid. Or if you've ever heard of people who brag about being hackers, but then all they do is use other people's scripts to do certain tasks. And all they can achieve is what that script can do. Nothing beyond that. That's a script kid.

Speaker 1

Ah, okay. I see.

Speaker 2

Yeah.

Speaker 1

All right. And one last question. What helps you to address vulnerable dependence within your projects in the event that you have them? I don't know. Oh.

Speaker 2

Okay. Well, before, before AI, it was a thing of, going through the code, at least sometimes you'll find that some of the vulnerabilities, they are self-explanatory because, I mean, if you're working on the code, the logs will always tell you, okay, this is where the issue is. Then you try to address it. Maybe it was just a misconfigured system or maybe it's an overload that you maybe overload as the system grows, right?

So before AI, there was a time when you could just go through the codes. I still do that because, I mean, some of the vulnerabilities, some of that I can just pinpoint and you work on it. But now with AI, sometimes you can just take patches of the codes that are non-sensitive, try to use AI for quick results. If it explains to you what it is, maybe try out its suggestions, that is off production because you don't want to work on a flying plane yeah so that's so yeah usually at least uh like now my company is adopted to say okay yes we can use AI to a certain level of course there are certain uh what can I say

We have to work with it within certain confinements. We don't just blindly use it because it's exposing a lot of vulnerability. People to a lot of vulnerabilities. But other than that, usually almost all our code, it is logs that we track all the time. So even if it's a small warning to us, we usually try and flag it and see what it is before it becomes an error. If it's an error, the same, we just need, we just address it. So it's just sense on code and also sometimes use AI when necessary. Yeah. I hope that answers your question. Yeah, yeah, I once answered someone like that and they were like, I once answered someone like that and I was like, bro, that's fake.

And I was like, okay, then just give me the code and let me do it because there's no better. Because I mean, if you write your code, right, and for some reason, it indicates that there's an error, the only way to solve it is go through the code. And if you are logging, like let's say if you use Winston, Winston student logging, it will log all your errors. It will pinpoint, okay, your code is running up to this time, and it fails at this point.

So you know exactly where to log. If you don't know where to log, then Probably just to solve the whole project and start again.

Speaker 1

All right. Thank you so much for taking your time to participate in this interview.

Speaker 2

No, it's a pleasure. I hope this helps you. If it doesn't, well, it was too good talking to you.

Speaker 1

Thank you so much.